

Physiology-consistent in-situ measurement of foliar methane flux using a closed-dynamic leaf chamber

Md Rezaul Karim¹, Md Abdul Halim¹, Sean C. Thomas¹

¹*Institute of Forestry and Conservation, John H. Daniels Faculty of Architecture, Landscape, and Design, University of Toronto, 33 Willcocks Street, Toronto, ON, M5S 3B3, Canada*

We present a novel in situ closed-dynamic leaf-chamber approach that enables high-sensitivity quantification of net foliar methane (CH₄) exchange under tightly controlled irradiance, leaf temperature, vapor pressure deficit (VPD), and boundary-layer conditions, supporting trace-gas measurements while maintaining physiologically realistic leaf function.

Methodology

Conventional foliar CH₄ exchange measurements have largely relied on static chambers with syringe sampling and gas chromatography, which offer limited temporal resolution and often perturb leaf microclimate and stomatal function ¹, reducing reliability when quantifying low flux rates. To address these limitations, we coupled an off-axis integrated cavity output spectroscopy analyzer (Los Gatos Research, USA) with a newly developed dynamic leaf chamber (CS-LC7000, CredoSense Inc., Canada) designed to preserve physiologically realistic gas-exchange conditions ². The chamber operates in a recirculating closed-dynamic configuration with continuous mixing, rapid headspace turnover (<60 s), and active control of irradiance, temperature, humidity, and vapor pressure deficit (VPD). This design prevents trace-gas accumulation, maintains near-ambient CO₂ and H₂O concentrations, and minimizes boundary-layer artifacts that commonly bias static or large-volume chambers. Net foliar methane exchange was quantified on intact, attached leaves of *Salix bebbiana* across a controlled irradiance gradient (0–2000 μmol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ PPFD), enabling construction of full CH₄ light-response curves analogous to standard photosynthetic measurements. Following each irradiance step, leaves were allowed to acclimate, and measurements were conducted under stable leaf temperature (26 °C) and VPD (1.6 kPa) to ensure consistent physiological conditions. This framework enables CH₄ exchange to be interpreted directly in relation to concurrent photosynthetic activity and transpiration, rather than as artifacts of chamber-induced stress.

Results

Microclimate stability and physiological integrity

The closed-dynamic leaf-chamber system maintained stable and physiologically realistic conditions throughout the irradiance sequence, supporting robust interpretation of trace-gas exchange across light steps. Mean leaf surface temperature was 26.08 ± 0.27 °C (SE) and mean relative humidity was 65.01 ± 2.29%, corresponding to a mean VPD of 1.61 kPa with a narrow-observed range (0.65–1.79 kPa). These stable conditions minimized irradiance-independent variability in stomatal behavior and reduced

enclosure-driven artifacts associated with temperature and humidity drift that commonly bias static chamber workflows.

Net foliar CH₄ exchange across the irradiance gradient

Under these controlled conditions, the system resolved net foliar CH₄ exchange across the full irradiance gradient (0–2000 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD), including near-background fluxes that are typically difficult to quantify in situ. Fluxes were derived from linear concentration change over 60-s measurement windows (median $R^2 = 0.99$). In darkness (0 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD), net CH₄ exchange remained small but consistently resolvable, on the order of $\sim 0.05\text{--}0.10$ $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. With increasing irradiance, net CH₄ uptake increased rapidly at low light (≤ 200 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD), reaching approximately 0.6–0.9 $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. At higher irradiance, CH₄ uptake followed a convex, saturating response, stabilizing under light-saturated conditions (>1500 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD). Maximum net CH₄ uptake reached 1.59 $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, consistent with a physiological saturation pattern rather than analytical limitation.

Repeatability and coupling to leaf gas transport

Replicate 60-s exchange windows separated by ambient recovery periods produced highly consistent slopes (CV < 1%), indicating minimal drift across cycles. Concurrent H₂O flux increased monotonically with irradiance, reaching a maximum of 138.95 $\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ under light-saturated conditions. The co-variation of increasing CH₄ uptake with rising H₂O flux across the irradiance gradient is consistent with stomatal and internal transport pathways contributing to net foliar CH₄ exchange, rather than progressive enclosure stress. The overall response shape closely mirrors canonical CO₂ and H₂O light-response patterns, reinforcing the value of acquiring trace-gas exchange under tightly controlled microclimate conditions.

Conclusion and implications

Collectively, these results demonstrate that the closed-dynamic, microclimate-controlled leaf-chamber approach enables reliable quantification of minute-scale net foliar CH₄ exchange across realistic irradiance gradients while maintaining stable leaf physiological conditions. The ability to resolve near-background exchange under both dark and light-saturated conditions supports stronger mechanistic interpretation of foliar methane dynamics and provides a measurement framework suitable for process studies and integration into methane accounting, modeling, and MRV-oriented workflows.

Figure

Figure 1. Light-response of net foliar gas exchange measured on intact *Salix bebbiana* leaves using a closed-dynamic, microclimate-controlled leaf chamber coupled to OA-ICOS. Panels show (a) CH₄ oxidation, (b) net photosynthesis, (c) transpiration, and (d) stomatal conductance versus photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD). Data points represent the mean ± SE. Solid lines indicate fitted model regressions. Microclimate stability (mean leaf temperature and VPD ± 95% CI) across measurement steps is shown as an inset in panel (d).

References

1. Farquhar, G. D. & Sharkey, T. D. Stomatal conductance and photosynthesis. Annual Review of Plant Biology vol. 33 317–345 (1982).
2. Karim, M. R., Halim, M. A. & Thomas, S. C. Foliar methane and nitrous oxide fluxes in *Salix bebbiana* respond to light and soil factors. Communications Earth & Environment 6, 493 (2025).